

Coenzyme B₁₂ model studies : Spectroscopic characterization and antibacterial activity of cobaloximes

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Abstract : The alkyl(ligand)cobaloximes were synthesized and characterized by IR, NMR and electronic data, where ligand = O and S donor ligands. The spectral data is correlated to the steric hindrance, HSAB principle and $d\pi-p\pi$ bonding from metal to ligand. It is found that S donor ligands form more stable complexes than O donor ligands. Their antibacterial activities are comparable to certain antibiotics such as bacitracin and tetracycline.

Keywords : Cobaloximes, spectroscopic characterization, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Schrauzer's¹ discovery of bis(dimethylglyoximato) complexes of cobalt, cobaloximes, the classic models for vitamin B₁₂ have been represented as RCo(DH)₂L (Structure 1, where DH = mono anion of dimethyl glyoxime, R = alkyl group, L = Lewis base). Cobaloximes^{2,3} have become the center of increasing chemical interest, since the most important property of cobaloximes is the ability to form very stable Co-C bonds. Cobaloximes have been extensively studied both in solution and in the solid state⁴⁻⁹.

Structure 1. Methyl(ligand)cobaloxime.

Coordination compounds containing O and S donor ligands are of considerable importance perhaps due to their antibacterial activity^{10,11}. Thiosemicarbazide complexes are found to possess prominent antibacterial activity¹². Thiosemicarbazones have activity against small pox¹³, virus¹⁴ and tuberculosis¹⁵. The study of

semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone compounds has received great impetus in recent years possibly due to their remarkable potential in inhibiting ribonucleotide reductase an obligatory enzyme in DNA synthesis^{16,17}. As a consequence these pharmacophores have been evaluated for their antiproliferative properties against a variety of tumors¹⁸ and antifungal¹⁹ properties. The biological activities of the thiosemicarbazone ligands have been attributed to their trace metal complexing abilities and the metal compounds have been generally found to possess enhanced therapeutic properties^{20,21}. Canpolat *et al.*²² reported that *vic*-dioximato complexes of Co^{III} complexes were the most active and may be promising for the development of new antibiotics. Recently Satyanarayana *et al.*²³⁻²⁵ has reported the antibacterial activity of methyl(ligand)cobaloximes (where ligand = pyrazole, dimethyl pyrazole, alanine and alanine methyl ester) and mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(III).

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectral data (Table 1) of the CH₃Co(DH)₂L complexes show the most intense band in the highest energy region ($\sim 36000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) have been assigned to Co^{III} $d\pi-p\pi^*(\text{DH})$ MLCT transition of the equatorial ligand. The lowest energy band ($\sim 22000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) has been assigned to a Co-C charge transfer transition²⁶ due to R⁻ to Co^{III} is a spin-allowed $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ transition²⁷, and this band disappears or is drastically decreased in alkyl (ligand)

Table 1. UV-Visible spectral data^a for CH₃Co(DH)₂L

Sl. no.	Complex	UV-Visible data		
		Peak-1	Peak-2	Peak-3
1.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ H ₂ O	22675.3	27700.8	32258.0
2.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ U	22935.3	26420.1	32948.9
3.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ FA	22935.8	26420.1	32948.9
4.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TU	23201.9	26420.1	33222.6
5.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ AC	23068.1	26954.2	34662.0
6.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TAC	22935.8	26246.7	32948.9
7.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TSC	22935.8	26595.7	32948.9
8.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ SC	22935.8	26420.1	32948.9

^aValue in cm⁻¹.

cobaloximes due to σ donation by the ligand. The $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ band is masked by the intense CT bands. Bands occurring at ~ 26500 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the L \rightarrow Co^{III}, LMCT. The σ DH \rightarrow σ^* Co^{III} is masked by the intense short wavelength bands of alkyl(ligand)cobaloximes²⁸. The Co-C CT band shifts to shorter wavelengths with decreasing electron-donating ability of the axial base²⁹.

Marzilli *et al.*³⁰, described the first application of near-IR excited Raman (near IR-FT Raman) spectroscopy to study photo-labile methyl cobaloxime. From the IR data (Table 2) it is analysed that disappearance of the peak at

3072 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a new peak at 450 cm⁻¹ ν (Co-N) indicates the formation of methyl(ligand)-cobaloxime by replacing H₂O. The IR spectra of free ligands were compared with the IR spectra of their corresponding cobaloxime complexes in order to identify the diagnostic bands.

From the experiments of Blinc and Hadzi³¹, we could assign the peaks around 1235 and 1100 cm⁻¹ to the N-O stretching vibrations. These two bands are shifted to higher wave numbers when the fifth ligand changes from H₂O to amide which is in the approximate order of the strength of electron donating power. The increase in the electron density in the N-O bond is considered to cause the high frequency shift of the vibration. The band around 508 cm⁻¹ is assignable to Co-N stretching frequency between Co^{III} and nitrogen atoms of dimethylglyoximato ligands. The Co-N vibration is shifted to higher wave numbers when water is substituted by amides and thioamide.

The characteristic absorption bands due to the amides and thioamide derivatives show weak bands at 3000–3300 cm⁻¹ due to N-H stretching vibrations. The band at 1600–1670 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C=O stretching. The band at 750–770 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C=S stretching. The C-H stretching of alkyl group linked to Co atom occurring at 2930 cm⁻¹.

Table 2. IR data^a of CH₃Co(DH)₂L^b

Sl. no.	Complex	DH				L			
		N(CH ₃)	ν (C=N)	ν (NO)	ν (Co-N)	ν (Co-O)	ν (C=S)	ν (C=O)	ν (N-H)
1.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ H ₂ O	1360.8	1575.0	1084.6	508.8	-	-	-	-
		1435.7		1225.6					
2.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ U	1374.2	1550.8	1087.9	516.2	260.0	-	1595.8	3216.6
		1474.0		1228.2				(1606.1)	
3.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ FA	1372.2	1559.7	1089.7	507.2	271.3	-	1569.7	3089.8
		1443.1		1231.5				(1709)	
4.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TU	1417.8	1507.7	1085.0	515.6	-	731.3	-	3178.0
		1473.2		1229.6			(738)		
5.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ AC	1372.4	1574.0	1085.7	511.8	261	-	1669.2	3113.8
		1455.6		1230.4				(1679.6)	
6.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TAC	1374.2	1576.9	1084.3	512.1	-	748.2	-	3199.8
		1456.4		1231.2			(750)		
7.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TSC	1416.4	1579.5	1084.4	515.3	-	731.0	-	3166.0
		1473.4		1229.6			(800)		
8.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ SC	1390.9	1573.8	1085.0	512.8	251.0	-	1681.7	3435.8
		1485.0		1229.8				(1691.8)	

^aRecorded as KBr discs and values in cm⁻¹.^bL, U = Urea, FA = Formamide, TU = Thiourea, AC = Acetamide, TAC = Thioacetamide, TSC = Thiosemicarbazide and SC = Semicarbazide.() Free ligand values in cm⁻¹.

However the definite relationship between the frequency shifts and the consecutive order of axial ligands was observed as mentioned i.e. H₂O < amide < thioamide. In short, as the donating power of the base ligand increases, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ at $\sim 1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifts to a lower wave number region while, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ at $\sim 1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1085 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{N})$ at $\sim 510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifts to higher one. These results can be interpreted as follows : the coordination of more electron donating base to Co atom causes the increase in electron density on Co atom which facilitates the back donation from Co to the nitrogen atoms of dimethylglyoximate ligands resulting in the increase in electron densities in C=N and N-O bonds. The increase in electron density in N-O bonds causes the stronger hydrogen bridges of O-H...O and higher frequency shifts of N-O stretching vibrations. The facilitated back donation from cobalt to nitrogen atoms of dimethylglyoxime lowers C=N stretching frequency. The definite relationship between the frequency shifts and the consecutive order of axial ligands was observed which shows that thioamides bind strongly than amide.

The ¹H NMR data (Table 3) of the complexes shows well resolved peaks corresponding to the axial methyl and equatorial methyl groups of dimethylglyoxime (DH). The sharp signals at 0.5 and 2.20 ppm integrating in the

Table 3. ¹H NMR data^a of CH₃Co(DH)₂L^b

Sl. no.	Complex	(CH ₃)	CH ₃ Co	-NH ₂ /-NH	-CH/-CH ₃ ^c
1.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ H ₂ O	2.10	0.5	-	-
2.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ U	2.20	0.4	5.20 (5.38)	-
3.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ FA	2.20	0.4	5.0 (6.72)	7.80 (8.21)
4.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TU	2.20	0.6	6.80 (6.60)	-
5.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ AC	2.20	0.4	5.40 (5.94)	2.50 (2.02)
6.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TAC	2.10	0.4	8.0 (7.09)	2.50 (2.58)
7.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ TSC	2.20	0.4	7.50 (7.81)	-
8.	CH ₃ Co(DH) ₂ SC	2.10	0.4	9.80 (10.06)	-
				9.0 (9.06)	

^aIn ppm relative to tetramethylsilane.

^bL, U = Urea, FA = Formamide, TU = Thiourea, AC = Acetamide, TAC = Thioacetamide, TSC = Thiosemicarbazide and SC = Semicarbazide.

^c-CH/-CH₃ of the ligand.

ratio 1 : 4 have been assigned to the *trans* CH₃ group (axial) and the four CH₃ groups (of DMG), respectively. It is seen that in methyl(ligand)cobaloximes that the *cis* and *trans* methyl groups are distinctively different. In CH₃Co(DH)₂U complex, the signals observed at 5.20 and

5.60 ppm (-NH₂) and CH₃Co(DH)₂SC complex, the signals observed at 9.80 and 9.0 ppm (-NH₂) indicating that the only one of the -NH₂ groups is involved in resonance with the -C=O and hence there is an upfield shift. In complexes CH₃Co(DH)₂FA and CH₃Co(DH)₂AC, the signals at 5.0 and 5.40 ppm correspond to -NH₂, which are shifted to up field as compared to free ligand (6.72 and 5.94 ppm). Same is the trend in the corresponding thioamides.

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial activities of the synthesized complexes were determined *in vitro* by standard disc diffusion method. It is found that all the complexes are exhibiting inhibition against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. From the zones of inhibition (Table 4) it is found that cobaloximes were found to be more effective than antibiotic, bacitracin. From the bar graphs (Fig. 1), the comparative activities can be analysed. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (Table 5) were also determined for the complexes. This shows that the cobaloximes may be promising for the development of broad range antibiotics.

Materials and methods : Methyl(aqua)cobaloximes were prepared by the procedure of Brown *et al.*³². All manipulations were performed under minimal illumination due to photolability of the organo cobalt bond³³. Methyl(ligand)cobaloximes were isolated by mixing 1 : 1 ratio of methyl(aqua)cobaloximes and the base ligand (L) in methanol. This mixture was heated at 40-50 °C by constant stirring for 1-2 h. Then the minimum amount of distilled water was added, the resulting yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with distilled water, followed by 95% methanol and ether and dried *in vacuo* (yields were 70-80%). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 200 MHz NMR spectrometer. Samples were prepared by dissolving in CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆. Infrared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR-1605 spectrometer using KBr pellets. The antimicrobial activities of the compounds were determined *in vitro* using different microorganisms by the standard disc diffusion method³⁴. The following bacteria were used : *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 1234), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC 1234), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 1234) and *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 1234). Bacterial cultures were sub-cultured in nutrient broth medium and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h and the logarithmic or exponential phase was

Table 4. Antimicrobial activity of the $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{L}$ complexes at $20 \mu\text{g/ml}^a$

Sl. no.	Complex	Bacterial species			
		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
1.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10	6	7	5
2.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{U}$	7	7	12	9
3.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TU}$	7	8	12	7
4.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{FA}$	9	7	11	7
5.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{AC}$	9	7	7	5
6.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TAC}$	5	4	12	9
7.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{SC}$	7	7	9	-
8.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TSC}$	8	11	12	9
	Tetracycline		10-14		
	Bacitracin		6-8		

^aValues of zone of inhibition [mm, including the diameter of the disc].

Fig. 1. Bar graphs of the relative antibacterial activity of the complexes. A = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; B = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{U}$; C = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TU}$; D = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{FA}$; E = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{AC}$; F = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TAC}$; G = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{SC}$; H = $\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TSC}$. (■) *E. coli*, (□) *K. pneumoniae*, (▨) *S. aureus*, (▩) *B. subtilis*.

Table 5. MIC^a of chemotherapeutic agent

Sl. no.	Complex	MIC (μg)
1.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	20
2.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{U}$	60
3.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TU}$	30
4.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{FA}$	20
5.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{AC}$	25
6.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TAC}$	30
7.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{SC}$	30
8.	$\text{CH}_3\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2\text{TSC}$	30

^aMinimum inhibitory concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$.

achieved. Filter paper discs of 4 mm size were prepared by using Whatmann filter paper no. 1, and on to each of

these discs a 5 ml of a solution of the complex in DMSO was added. At the end of the incubation period the zones of inhibition were measured.

Conclusions : From this study it is found that methyl-(ligand)cobaloxime forms more stable complexes with thioamides (soft donor) than amides (hard donor) whose stability has been explained on the basis of basicity of the incoming ligand, steric hindrance, HSAB principle and $d\pi-p\pi$ back bonding. The above complexes show activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, which reveals their promising antibacterial activity for the development of broad range antibiotics.

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